

Interphase Analysis of Polyamide66 Laminates with Protonated and Deuterated Polymers

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Introduction

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Adhesion
Composites

Interface

Performance

Buried
Limitation

<Same polymer interface>

Same chemical structure

**Difficult to
evaluate structure!!**

Introduction

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Deuterated polymers

Structure & physical properties **Very similar**

Spectroscopic & neutron contrast

Interfacial analyses

Characterization

&

Interfacial analysis
by nano-Raman

Sample preparation

3

Interfacial polycondensation

In water

In hexane

Spectroscopic properties

4

Interfacial analysis

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Nano-Raman spectroscopy

ALPHA 300R (WITec)

- Laser power 10 mW
- Wave length 532 nm
- Spatial resolution 300 nm
- Magnification × 100

Annealing

Change of

interfacial structure

T. Nishino et al, *Polymer*, **53**, 1966-1971(2012)

H-PA66/D-PA66 laminated film

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Nano-Raman spectroscopy

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As-quenched laminate

Fig. Nano-Raman spectra across the H-PA66/D-PA66 interface.

As-quenched laminate

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<Microscopic image>

<Raman 2D image for $\nu(\text{CD}_2)$ >

Fig. Raman integrated intensity profiles across the H-PA66 / D-PA66 interface of as-quenched laminate for CH_2 and CD_2 stretching band.

Abrupt change

Annealed laminate

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<Microscopic image>

<Raman 2D image for $\nu(\text{CD}_2)$ >

Fig. Raman integrated intensity profiles across the H-PA66 / D-PA66 interface of annealed laminate for CH_2 and CD_2 stretching band.

Gradual change

Differential profiles @ interphase

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Fig. Differential intensity curves calculated from Raman integrated intensity profiles across the H-PA66 / D-PA66 interphase of as-quenched and annealed laminate for CD₂ stretching band.

The influence of crystallinity

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<Previous experiment>

<Crystallized laminate>

The interphase of crystallized laminate

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Fig. Differential intensity curves calculated from Raman integrated intensity profiles across the H-PA66 / D-PA66 interphase of crystallized laminate for CD_2 stretching band before and after annealing.

Adequately crystallized

~~Mutual crystal growth~~

Conclusions

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Same polymer interphase

<Characterization>

Same

- Crystalline structure
- Thermal properties
- Surface property

Different Spectroscopic properties

<Interphase analysis>

Nano-Raman

Financially Supports

<Interphase thickness>

1.3 μm

Annealing

2.9 μm

Lamellae interlocking